

A Standardized Evaluation of QoS/QoE Performance in 5G and Beyond-5G Systems

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Abstract—Since their deployment and commercialization, 5th Generation (5G) mobile systems have been extensively analyzed to quantify the Quality of Service and Experience (QoS/QoE) achievable by heterogeneous services. Real-time interactive services, i.e., applications within the scope of Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communication (URLLC) and at the intersection of URLLC and enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB), are, however, often tested using simplistic methodologies that do not provide accurate assessments. In this paper, we extend our previous work on the empirical characterization of mobile networks by presenting a comprehensive analysis of a methodology standardized by the International Telecommunication Union Telecommunication Standardization Sector (ITU-T). This methodology is designed for systematic and reproducible QoS/QoE evaluations of real-time interactive services. We validate it through dedicated measurements (for which we open-source the corresponding dataset along with this paper) in the Karlstad University testbed, i.e., a private network supporting 5G connectivity modes and features beyond those available in current public networks in Sweden. Our results, spanning across services, mobility scenarios, connectivity modes, and servers, provide key insights into the intricate dependencies between QoS/QoE, environmental conditions, and system configurations, ultimately serving as a foundation for designing high-performing beyond-5G mobile systems.

I. INTRODUCTION

Standardized by the 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) in Release 15 (Rel-15), the Fifth Generation (5G) New Radio (NR) system was designed to address the Quality of Service and Experience (QoS/QoE) demands of different verticals. Compared to Fourth Generation (4G) Long Term Evolution (LTE) and LTE-Advanced systems, several enhancements were conceived, e.g., novel Radio Access Network (RAN) and Core Network (CN), and Standalone (SA) and Non-Standalone (NSA) deployments. Some of these solutions are already used in public networks (PN) and private or non-public networks (NPN), allowing for empirical research toward system improvement [1], [2].

To account for increasing system complexity and QoS/QoE requirement heterogeneity, performance testing methodologies should evolve along with systems and services. This is particularly relevant for *real-time interactive services*, i.e., use cases belonging to Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communication (URLLC) and in between URLLC and enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB), such as Augmented/Virtual Reality

(AR/VR), industrial automation, and transportation. Such verticals share a common need for a smooth interaction between clients and servers and were not supported by previous mobile generations. They thus require the definition and use of novel testing procedures and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).

On the one hand, standardization and stakeholder communities, e.g., the International Telecommunication Union Telecommunication Standardization Sector (ITU-T) and European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI), are carrying out several activities toward the definition of testing methodologies [3]–[5]. On the other hand, the research community is highlighting the importance of analyzing 5G and Beyond-5G (B5G) performance from a service perspective. However, testing has been mostly focused on eMBB, with real-time interactive cases often addressed via simplistic and/or proprietary methodologies, which hinder realistic and comparable QoS/QoE assessments (see [1], [2] for a review of related work).

Within the above context, this paper extends our previous work in [1] while keeping the main goal of providing a common ground to research, standardization, and stakeholder communities on systematic and reproducible QoS/QoE performance testing. Therefore, we first describe the methodology standardized by ITU-T for testing real-time interactive services in 5G/B5G networks [3]. Then, we present additional evidence that shows how this methodology enables reliable QoS/QoE benchmarking. Our assessment leverages a multi-service measurement campaign carried out in the 3GPP Rel-17 NPN of Karlstad University (KAU) [6], thus moving beyond [1], where we based our analyses on measurements collected in two Rel-15 Swedish PNs. The availability at KAU of hybrid LTE-A, 5G NSA, 5G SA connectivity and further enhanced features allows to assess how the methodology can be used in B5G networks, particularly highlighting how network evolution help improving the performance of interactive services compared to commercial deployments, currently limited in Sweden to LTE-A and 5G NSA connectivity. We also open-source our dataset for further use by the interested communities [7].

II. THE ITU-T METHODOLOGY FOR REAL-TIME INTERACTIVE SERVICE TESTING

Service latency, stability, and continuity are key aspects for real-time interactive applications, with tighter requirements

TABLE I

DESCRIPTION OF THREE TRAFFIC PATTERNS COMPLIANT WITH THE ITU-T RECOMMENDATION G.1051. FOR EACH PATTERN, THE VALUES FOR THE PARAMETERS TO USE IN THE I-SCORE MODEL ARE ALSO REPORTED, ACCORDING TO [3].

Name	Data Rate Profile [Mb/s]	Duration [s]	Min/Max Packet Size [Bytes]	Min/Max Packet Rate [pkt/s]	Round-Trip Delay Budget [ms]	<i>i</i> -score Model Parameters				
						f_{\max}	a	b	u	v
<i>eGaming real-time</i>		10	100	125/1250	100	100	61	14	120	4
<i>AR/VR Cloud Gaming</i>		10	5460/10920 (DL) 540 (UL)	60	100	100	61	14	120	4
<i>I4.0 Process Automation</i>		30	100	625	20	100	15	2	10	2500

compared to eMBB. Proper testing is thus needed for assessing these services from an *interactivity* perspective.

In Recommendation G.1051, ITU-T has standardized a methodology that can be used for measuring QoS/QoE of real-time interactive services in 5G/B5G systems [3]. By leveraging previous activities carried out by ETSI [4], [5], ITU-T provides guidelines for (i) defining traffic patterns that resemble service data flows, (ii) measuring a common set of QoS KPIs independently on the service under test, and (iii) modeling a QoE KPI, denoted as interactivity score (*i*-score [%]), as a service-specific function of the QoS KPIs.

A. Service Definition and Emulation

In a first step, the methodology requires to define a client-server pair and instantiate downlink (DL) and uplink (UL) data flows emulating real services.

1) *Concepts and Protocols*: The client, e.g., a 5G-capable User Equipment (UE), is a packet generating unit, and the server, hosting the service back-end, is a reflecting unit. In the simplest case, each client-generated packet is paired up with a server-reflected, same-size packet, leading to UL/DL-symmetric traffic flows. The methodology, however, requires the server to be able to reflect packets of different sizes, so as to mimic services characterized by UL/DL-asymmetric flows. During a test, packet size and rate can also change to emulate different service phases, ultimately forming a pattern representing applications in a same category.

Due to the focus on real-time services, the methodology specifies User Datagram Protocol (UDP) as the transport protocol. On top of UDP, it is recommended to use Two-Way Active Measurement Protocol (TWAMP), standardized by the Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) [8]. Since TWAMP enables same-size packet generation/reflection, ITU-T allows for proprietary protocol extensions. If UDP packets are fragmented due to their size exceeding the maximum transmission unit allowed on the client-server path, fragments

are transmitted sequentially and the receiving side reassembles them.

2) *Examples*: Similar to [1], we used three traffic patterns to characterize the ITU-T methodology in the network deployment at KAU. For these patterns, referred to in the following as *eGaming real-time*, *AR/VR Cloud Gaming*, and *Industry 4.0 (I4.0) Process Automation*, the characteristics in terms of data rate, duration, packet size and generation rate are given in Table I. *eGaming real-time* is a UL/DL-symmetric pattern that mimics the interaction of a user with a gaming platform, where low-to-medium data rates represent different interaction phases during which, however, only status information is exchanged between client and server, with video processing performed by the user. *AR/VR Cloud Gaming* is a UL/DL-asymmetric pattern derived by analyzing traffic generated by popular cloud gaming platforms. It thus mimics services where the client sends status information (e.g., head orientation) to a server, with a low data rate. The server processes this information and sends back high-definition video frames in three phases of medium-to-high-to-medium data rate. Finally, *I4.0 Process Automation* is a UL/DL-symmetric pattern based on I4.0 URLLC services, as described by 3GPP [9]. It mimics scenarios where sensor data are fed to a controller that configures actuators. Data rate is lower than in previous patterns but test duration is longer, with the aim of assessing service continuity.

B. Service QoS: latency, stability, and continuity

Once traffic patterns are defined, service latency, stability, and continuity can be quantified by measuring three QoS KPIs.

Latency is measured as the Round Trip Time (RTT) of each pair of UDP packets. Stability is measured as latency variation, following the IETF definition of Packet Delay Variation (PDV) [10], i.e., the difference between the RTT of a packet and the minimum RTT across all packets. Continuity is measured as Packet Loss Rate (PLR), i.e., the ratio between *disqualified* and client-scheduled packets. Packets are disqualified if not usable

Fig. 1. Examples of i -score models for *e-Gaming real-time*, *AR/VR Cloud Gaming*, and *I4.0 Process Automation*. Curves are derived by using the parameters of Table I, for different values of PLR and σ_{PDV} (i.e., the PDV standard deviation for non-disqualified packets [1]).

for a real-time service. They include not only lost but also discarded packets, i.e., packets received after an RTT budget. This budget is 100 ms for *eGaming real-time* and *AR/VR Cloud Gaming* (5G QoS Identifier (5QI) Class 3), and 20 ms for *I4.0 Process Automation* (5QI Class 82) [9], [11]. In case of fragmentation, a packet is disqualified if one fragment is disqualified. RTT and PDV are evaluated on the last fragment of non-disqualified packets.

C. Service QoE: the i -score KPI

Once service latency, stability, and continuity are quantified, the ITU-T methodology provides a way to evaluate a QoE KPI, the i -score, assessing client-perceived service responsiveness [3]–[5]. The i -score definition reflects the need for evaluating QoE also for services not involving humans. Therefore, a general way of assessing QoE is proposed, which leverages a service-agnostic model embedded with service-specific parameters, these latter reflecting heterogeneous requirements.

It is assumed that service interactivity has a monotonous inverse dependency on latency, with saturation areas at low/high latency. A logistic function with service-specific parameters f_{\max} , a , and b is thus used to model the dependency of interactivity on latency, so that RTTs from non-disqualified packets result in values between 0% and f_{\max} %, ultimately enabling the evaluation of $score_{RTT}$, the RTT-dependent term of the i -score model. PDV and PLR are then accounted for by defining $score_{PDV}$ and $score_{PLR}$, with u and v parameters. Finally, the i -score is the product between these three terms, as detailed in [1], [3], where equations for evaluating $score_{RTT}$, $score_{PDV}$, and $score_{PLR}$ are also reported.

Table I reports the i -score model parameters for the above services. To reflect the 3GPP mapping to the same application category, the i -score model for *e-Gaming real-time* and *AR/VR Cloud Gaming* uses the same parameters. Figure 1 shows examples of i -score curves, as a function of the underlying

QoS KPIs, highlighting how different parameters and service requirements affect the model. For example, *I4.0 Process Automation* requires extremely low RTT to achieve a high i -score, and is more affected by stability and continuity degradation compared to gaming and AR/VR applications.

III. MEASUREMENT METHODOLOGY

We now describe the methodology adopted in this paper for assessing the ITU-T procedure. We particularly detail the setup, campaign, and dataset.

A. Setup

We performed our measurement campaign in the 3GPP Rel-17 NPN available at KAU, also referred to as CARL-W, i.e., Communications Advanced Research Laboratory – Wireless module [6].

CARL-W is part of NorthStar, a joint venture led by Telia and Ericsson that supports research in the context of mobile systems, by providing system features beyond commercially available solutions [12]. CARL-W thus supports a hybrid 4G-5G RAN and CN, jointly enabling LTE-A, 5G NSA, and 5G SA connectivity. This deployment significantly departs from the PNPs available in Sweden at the time of writing (March 2025) and analyzed in [1], limited to LTE-A and 5G NSA and using a 4G CN.

As depicted in Fig. 2, CARL-W provides indoor and outdoor coverage. For the indoor deployment, two multi-floor buildings are covered with dedicated RAN elements, i.e., House 21 (Engineering building) and the Innovation Park building, spaced out by around 500 meters. Each building hosts an indoor radio unit which terminates in four (House 21) vs. one (Innovation Park) 4G/5G radio dot pairs. The dots at House 21 operate with the same Physical Cell Identifier (PCI) and provide seamless connectivity with no PCI (re-)selections and handovers. 4G operates in Band 7, adopting Frequency Division Duplexing (FDD) and 20 MHz each for DL/UL. 5G operates in Band n78, using Time Division Duplexing (TDD), a 100 MHz channel, a 30 kHz subcarrier spacing, and a TDD pattern with 3 DL slots, 1 special slot (10 DL symbols, 2 flexible symbols, and 2 UL symbols), and 1 UL slot.

For the outdoor deployment, CARL-W covers the entire KAU campus, by leveraging three outdoor radio units providing 4G/5G service via several PCIs. As for the indoor case, some 4G and 5G PCIs operate in Bands 7 and n78. Moreover, other 4G PCIs operate in Bands 3, 8, 20, 28, and 38, and other 5G PCIs operate in Band n28. Cell (re-)selections and handovers allow for UEs to move across outdoor sites and between outdoor and indoor sites. In terms of connectivity policies, CARL-W is configured so that 5G SA is prioritized over 5G NSA and LTE-A. Fallback to 5G NSA/LTE-A is triggered in situations of poor/absent 5G coverage; transitions from LTE-A and 5G NSA to 5G SA are triggered when the UE releases its 4G connection. Finally, CARL-W leverages a Multiple Operator Core Network (MOCN) setup, thus sharing RAN sites and frequency resources (with different indoor/outdoor splits) with the Telia PN active on campus, so to minimize NPN-PN interference.

Fig. 2. Diagram showing the CARL-W deployment at KAU.

Moving to the CN, as depicted in Fig. 2, CARL-W user and control planes are fully decoupled. While the main control plane functionalities are instantiated in dedicated servers in Stockholm (300 km from Karlstad), a Local BreakOut (LBO) allows for deploying 5G User Plane Function (UPF) and 4G Packet Gateway (PGW) in edge servers on campus. This reduces the user plane network path and, in turn, data latency.

B. Campaign

We run measurements in the KAU campus in January-March 2025, using a 5G-capable UE (CrossCall Stellar-X5) embedded with the Rohde & Schwarz (R&S) Qualipoc Android app. Measurement replay, inspection, and data exporting were carried out on an Intel Windows PC running ROMES, a R&S software enabling such operations.

We organized our measurements in Indoor Static (IS), Indoor Walking (IW), and Outdoor Walking (OW) campaigns, covering 7 IS, 1 IW, and 3 OW locations served by CARL-W. For each location, we repeated measurements over different days. We used the UE to execute performance tests, configuring it to operate in two modes, i.e., LTE-Only (LTE-O), that forced the UE to only expose 4G capabilities, and 5G-Enabled (5G-E), that enabled the UE to expose 5G capabilities, so that it can connect in 5G SA and NSA, depending on coverage conditions and connectivity policies.

We primarily performed *interactivity tests*, via a Qualipoc routine that makes it possible to run tests following the ITU-T methodology. We ran tests with *eGaming real-time*, *AR/VR Cloud Gaming*, and *I4.0 Process Automation* patterns, after installing the service back-end in two servers, one in a private edge in the KAU campus (SE-K) and one in a public cloud in Stockholm (SE-S). Tests were repeated several times for each campaign. In the following, a single repetition is referred to as a *session*. For additional analyses, we performed Internet Control Message Protocol (ICMP) ping tests in one IS location, by transmitting 32-byte pings with a period of 10, 50, 100, 500, 1000, 5000, and 10000 ms toward both servers, in the same locations and conditions of the interactivity tests.

C. Dataset

In 5G-E mode, we ran about 2500 interactivity sessions across scenarios, patterns, and servers, with a slightly higher percentage of IS sessions. We also collected about 10000 ping RTT values toward our servers. The 5G-E mode led to more than 90% of sessions executed in 5G SA, due to its prioritized use over 5G NSA and LTE in CARL-W. We ran about twice as many measurements in 5G-E mode as in LTE-O mode. The collected dataset includes information on QoS/QoE performance observed during each session, i.e.,

application-layer DL/UL throughput, RTT, PDV, PLR, and *i-score* of the interactivity tests, and ping RTTs. Additionally, it includes coverage indicators, e.g., Reference Signal Received Power/Quality (RSRP/RSRQ) and Signal-to-Interference plus Noise Ratio (SINR) of the 4G/5G PCIs at which the UE was connected during tests, as well as resource allocation information, e.g., Modulation and Coding Scheme (MCS) and Transport Block Size (TBS).

In this paper, we specifically analyze 2 IS and 2 OW locations, as they form a representative sample to address the scope of this work, i.e., methodology validation. However, we open-source the entire dataset in [7] for further use by research, standardization, and stakeholder communities, also jointly with our previously open-sourced dataset measured on two Swedish PNs and used in [1].

IV. RESULTS

In this section, we analyze the collected measurements, so to provide a data-driven characterization of the ITU-T methodology.

A. A preliminary discussion on ICMP ping

In [1], we showed significant performance differences between interactivity and ping tests across two PNs in terms of RTT values, also due to different strategies that operators apply for handling non-data protocols like ICMP. We thus concluded that the use of ping for evaluating real service performance in 5G/B5G networks should be avoided, in line with previous work (e.g., [13]). Figure 3 complements this analysis by reporting, in a boxplot format, the RTT values measured in CARL-W during ping tests, as a function of the ping period and server location. Results refer to 5G-E tests in one IS location (Location 1 in Table II). We observe a significant impact of the ping period on RTT values, with the latter showing a minimum median of 8-9 ms (SE-K) and 15-16 ms (SE-S) when the ping period is between 10-100 ms. For both servers, the RTT values increase with the ping period, reaching 21-24 ms (SE-K) and 29-34 ms (SE-S) when the ping period is between 500-5000 ms, and eventually peaking to around 190 ms when the ping period is 10 seconds. Although a detailed discussion is beyond the scope of this work, we observe that these results are directly related to the default Discontinuous Reception (DRX) configuration adopted in CARL-W. This configuration instructs UEs to periodically enter in sleep states to improve battery power consumption, while remaining connected. Scheduling and exchange of ping packets are thus delayed when the ping period is higher than 100 ms, as this negatively interacts with the DRX period, which is also higher than 100 ms, causing the RTT increase (see [14] for additional analyses leading to similar conclusions). When the ping period is 10 seconds, we observe an even more extreme situation, with the UE moving from connected to idle mode during this interval. Therefore, the transmission of a new ping packet also requires connection re-establishment, causing additional delays and the RTT peak.

Overall, these results further highlight the issues faced when using ping for quantifying latency performance in 5G/B5G

Fig. 3. RTT values measured during ICMP ping tests in one IS location, as a function of the ping period, for SE-K (left) and SE-S (right) servers. Connectivity mode: 5G-E.

deployments: without properly setting up ping tests and DRX configurations (and document such settings when results are reported), ping RTT values result in low interpretability and potential inconsistency when compared to the latency experienced by real data packets.

B. QoS/QoE performance benchmarking

Table II reports the median values and standard deviations of QoS (RTT, PDV, and PLR) and QoE (*i-score*) KPIs measured and evaluated during the interactivity sessions executed in 2 IS and 2 OW locations, as a function of traffic pattern, connectivity mode, and server location. Following ITU-T guidelines, RTT and PDV are evaluated for non-disqualified packets and, thus, “–” in the table means that all packets were disqualified (for these cases, PLR is indeed 100%).

1) Impact of traffic patterns and service requirements:

We first analyze performance across services to discover that, although *eGaming real-time* and *AR/VR Cloud Gaming* have the same *i-score* model parameters (Table I), the latter reaches a slightly higher median *i-score* than the former during 5G-E tests, while the opposite is observed during LTE-O tests. This is explained by the RTT and PDV trends, that highlight a higher RTT and a lower PDV for *AR/VR Cloud Gaming* compared to *eGaming real-time*, with differences up to 5 ms for both KPIs. The median PLR is instead always 0%, i.e., packets swiftly meet the RTT budget of 100 ms and thus PLR does not affect the observed *i-score*. The UL/DL traffic for the two services is the main reason for such RTT/PDV variations, with the bigger DL packets of *AR/VR Cloud Gaming* leading to higher RTT but also lower PDV, as they better fit radio transport blocks and do not need to be queued and aggregated before being transmitted by the radio interface. Hence, although the above trade-off between RTT and PDV is observed for both 5G-E and LTE-O sessions, the actual values of the two parameters lead to a higher *i-score* for *AR/VR Cloud Gaming* in 5G-E and for *eGaming real-time* in LTE-O. When compared to the results obtained in PNs [1], significant *i-score* improvements are achieved for both

TABLE II
QoS/QoE PERFORMANCE OBSERVED IN 2 IS AND 2 OW LOCATIONS IN CARL-W
(eG: eGAMING REAL-TIME, A/VR: AR/VR CLOUD GAMING, I4.0: I4.0 PROCESS AUTOMATION).

Loc. ID	Scenario	Mode	Server	QoS / QoE KPIs per service (median and standard deviation)											
				RTT [ms]			PDV [ms]			PLR [%]			<i>i-score</i> [%]		
				eG	A/VR	I4.0	eG	A/VR	I4.0	eG	A/VR	I4.0	eG	A/VR	I4.0
1	IS	5G-E	SE-K	15.9	20.7	17.0	8.1	7.1	10.0	0	0	30.1	92.0	92.7	0
				0.83	0.26	0.10	0.80	0.35	0.28	0	0	2.58	1.23	0.37	0
			SE-S	25.0	27.1	19.2	9.6	7.5	10.3	0	0	97.1	88.4	89.9	0
		LTE-O	SE-K	1.50	0.33	0.03	11.74	0.80	0.30	21.06	0.74	1.42	22.85	3.59	0
				25.4	27.0	18.7	11.8	7.7	11.6	0	0	91.5	88.8	87.9	0
			SE-S	0.24	0.21	0.03	0.28	0.69	0.46	22.93	0.11	0.56	1.35	1.18	0
33.2	34.7	–	11.8	8.1	–	0	0	100	83.6	82.6	0				
0.27	0.38	–	0.47	0.57	–	0.06	0	0	1.16	0.74	0				
2	IS	5G-E	SE-K	22.9	23.7	18.8	10.1	5.4	10.8	0	0	88.3	89.9	90.8	0
				0.51	0.72	0.07	0.53	0.67	0.50	0.14	0.48	1.54	1.71	2.97	0
			SE-S	29.5	30.8	–	9.1	5.7	–	0	0	100	85.8	87.8	0
		LTE-O	SE-K	0.39	0.53	–	0.38	0.87	–	0	0	0	0.96	1.48	0
				31.1	36.2	19.6	13.4	11.3	13.0	0	0	99.9	84.0	79.6	0
			SE-S	0.56	0.50	0.11	0.56	1.29	0.39	0.04	0.72	0.05	1.55	2.52	0
38.4	41.8	–	12.9	10.4	–	0	0	100	78.2	73.8	0				
0.36	0.81	–	0.33	1.52	–	0.02	0.48	0	1.42	1.94	0				
3	OW	5G-E	SE-K	25.1	20.0	18.5	10.8	4.7	9.5	0	0	75.2	86.0	92.3	0
				4.81	1.71	0.52	3.09	1.68	1.73	1.74	0.53	15.65	8.96	3.23	0
			SE-S	29.2	31.7	–	8.9	8.2	–	0	0	100	86.0	85.8	0
		LTE-O	SE-K	0.49	1.02	–	1.65	1.57	–	0.43	0.21	0	3.14	1.99	0
				30.8	34.5	19.5	13.3	10.7	13.2	0	0	99.9	83.5	79.6	0
			SE-S	0.40	0.81	0.16	0.34	0.98	0.59	0.38	0.49	0.02	2.29	2.82	0
38.5	42.2	–	12.9	10.8	–	0	0	100	77.7	72.3	0				
0.64	1.17	–	0.71	1.37	–	0.20	0.75	0	1.79	3.81	0				
4	OW	5G-E	SE-K	21.6	23.3	18.6	8.7	6.3	9.7	0	0	77.9	89.6	90.5	0
				0.53	1.02	0.29	0.57	1.06	1.52	0.34	0.85	7.47	2.72	4.36	0
			SE-S	29.6	32.0	–	9.2	6.8	–	0	0	100	85.6	86.3	0
		LTE-O	SE-K	1.07	0.72	–	0.86	0.96	–	0.19	0.17	0	3.61	2.93	0
				30.8	35.3	19.6	13.1	11.1	13.1	0	0	99.9	83.6	80.3	0
			SE-S	0.50	1.03	0.17	0.62	1.07	0.62	0.34	0.83	0.04	2.27	5.09	0
38.3	42.3	–	12.7	10.2	–	0	0	100	78.1	73.4	0				
0.36	0.93	–	0.39	1.16	–	0.28	1.50	0	2.28	5.36	0				

patterns, which showcase the benefits of adopting dedicated network deployments for real-time interactive services.

Moving to *I4.0 Process Automation*, we observe a 0% *i-score* in all cases. In line with [1], this result confirms that the strict requirements of this service cannot be satisfied in current networks. In CARL-W, however, we observe a median PLR between 30-100% (SE-K server), i.e., in the best case, achieved in a location with high-quality 5G coverage (Location 1, see next), *only* 30% of packets experience an RTT higher than the service budget (20 ms). Although a median PLR of 30% is still too high for this service (see Figure 1), this value is significantly better than the values measured in PNs, where we observed a median PLR approaching 100% for the vast majority of sessions [1]. Our results show that a combination of high-quality SA connectivity and optimized data plane leads to promising improvements toward achieving full support for this service class. The ITU-T methodology can thus help highlighting the need for further improvements, opening the way for research on specific aspects, e.g., new solutions for URLLC support.

2) *Impact of locations and scenarios*: As reported in Table II, best performance is consistently achieved in Location 1, that is a location in House 21 where our UE was only less than 5 meters away from a 4G/5G radio dot pair, thus in line of sight and stably connected to it in both 5G-E and LTE-O

modes. Location 2 is instead an office in House 21 where our UE was connected to outdoor 4G/5G PCIs (around 300 meters away), since the indoor dots were not able to provide better coverage. Different coverage conditions, along with potentially different policies for handling NPN traffic in indoor/outdoor RAN sites (due to the MOCN setup), clearly reflect in the QoS/QoE performance measured via the ITU-T methodology, with Location 2 showing lower performance compared to Location 1. Closer results are observed between Locations 3 and 4, which indeed provide similar 5G/4G coverage. In terms of IS/OW scenarios, we observe a higher variability in the OW case, due to user mobility, PCI (re-)selections, and handovers.

The entire dataset in [7] includes additional locations and scenarios, thus providing a valuable input for further investigation, also toward deriving QoS/QoE prediction solutions for enhanced network management, e.g., by leveraging machine learning [15].

3) *Impact of connectivity mode and server placement*: As reported in Table II, a better median performance is consistently achieved in 5G-E mode and with the SE-K server, deployed in the CARL-W edge and, thus, closer to our client. Figure 4 further confirms this result, and also reveals that the *i-score* variability is often higher in LTE-O mode. On the one hand, these results align with previous results in [1], that highlighted the benefits of using 5G NSA instead of

Fig. 4. *i*-score measured during *eGaming* real-time and *AR/VR Cloud Gaming* sessions in IS (left) vs. OW (right) scenarios, as a function of server (SE-K / SE-S) and connectivity mode (5G-E / LTE-O).

4G for real-time interactive services. On the other hand, the lower *i*-score variability in 5G-E mode observed in CARL-W counteracts the results obtained over PNs, thus highlighting that dedicated NPNs (SA and/or NSA, the comparison of which is made possible by our dataset) can provide higher QoS/QoE stability when compared to PNs.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper extends [1] by providing a new data-driven analysis of the ITU-T methodology for assessing performance of real-time interactive services in 5G/B5G systems. In particular, we further validated the ability of the methodology in benchmarking QoS/QoE performance of services with heterogeneous characteristics and requirements, ultimately highlighting how continuous network evolution helps improving the performance of real-time interactive services. This was achieved by leveraging measurements in the NPN available at KAU, which supports features beyond current PNs in Sweden while being compliant with 3GPP Rel-17, ultimately ensuring that the obtained results are representative of 3GPP-compliant B5G systems and corresponding capabilities.

In future work, we plan to go beyond current limitations of the ITU-T methodology, by investigating ways to extend the methodology to other traffic patterns, while also studying how the *i*-score model can be refined by also taking into account results from subjective user testing, at least for service involving humans. We will also replicate our measurements in different deployments and further investigate the dependencies between QoS/QoE KPIs, coverage conditions, and network configurations. Our goal is to better understand such dependencies, toward deriving enhancement solutions and supporting a service-based design of next-generation systems.

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